

OPEN ONLINE COURSES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The modernization of the educational process and the provision of educational institutions with modern equipment are actively taking place. But at the same time, a fairly limited number of teachers and educators are still prepared to use information technologies (IT) in their activities. Nowadays pedagogical internet communities are poorly developed. This article discusses about open online courses in teaching Russian as a foreign language and how to conduct them efficiently. Of course, here is the fact that students can or cannot form certain competencies necessary in the modern information society.

For the educational process, all the necessary conditions must be created with regard to the use of IT technologies in the management of an educational institution.

It is important for a teacher to form an interest in achieving the planned tasks and goals for students in terms of mastering the educational program, including in the subject area "Russian language" with the use of Telegram messenger in the educational process.

The purpose of this study is to consider the existing electronic educational technologies and the features of their application for effective use in teaching practice in teaching Russian.

In education, you can see how state, commercial and public projects in the field of e-education are developing: the creation of electronic educational materials, including in Russian language, the use of educational mobile applications, the creation of electronic libraries and dictionaries. Progress is irreversible, and more and more educational institutions are provided with modern equipment. Our task is not to slow it down, but to find effective ways to introduce IT technologies into the educational environment: to train teachers to work with electronic educational technologies, and also to increase students' motivation for learning with their help, thereby forming the competencies they need in the modern information society.

Publishing houses have also joined this movement. In 1994, Simon and Schuster became one of the pioneers in this field by launching the New Media Group. Members of the New Media Group included future MP3 Newswire publisher Richard Ment, whose key project was the Guest Lecture Series. This Series was the first successful example of online video lectures in

universities. The introductory lecture was broadcast in December 1996 with Harvard Physics Professor Dr. Eric Mazur.

By 1994, the first online high school was founded. In 1997, criteria were formulated for courses based on new products and technologies to be portable, reproducible, scalable, accessible, and with a high likelihood of long-term cost-effectiveness.

The Open University in the UK and the University of British Columbia (part of Blackboard Inc.) have started a revolution in the use of the Internet for learning. They relied on intensive use of the Internet, interactive distance learning and online discussions between students.

The development of the Internet has made it possible to apply new interaction schemes using multimedia or webcams. The number of students enrolled in online learning programs increased by 65% from 2021 to 2022 [2], due to greater flexibility, ease of communication between teacher and student, as well as short lectures and feedback.

The main goal in teaching Russian is the formation of communicative competence. Other goals (educational, upbringing, developing) are already being implemented as part of the implementation of the main goal. It is important to note that communicative competence, in its modern sense, provides for the formation of the ability for intercultural interaction.

Today, the informatization of education is not only and not so much the provision of participants in the educational process with computer technology or their connection to the Internet. Nowadays, school informatization is an irreversible process of changing the content, methods and organizational forms of general educational training of students at the stage of school transition to work in the information society. To date, schools are still not sufficiently informatized. But informatization of the school is its expected transformation. This transformation is ideally aimed at ensuring that in the conditions of mass education in practice:

- ensure the availability of quality education for all;
- to help each student achieve new educational results, which are declared by the Federal State Educational Standard of the new generation;
- to turn our school into a school of cooperation. [3]

However, computers, electronic learning materials and technical connection to the Internet cannot automatically improve the efficiency of the educational process, do not lead to an increase in the quality of education without the active participation of teachers who are carriers of new generation educational technologies, who methodically correctly use the new information educational resource. It is necessary to constantly look for and develop new ways of learning based on ICT.

Although until now there is no single definition of e-learning, experts agree that this term can be understood as any pedagogical activity using modern electronic means.

As soon as electronic technologies and tools appeared, they were among the first to be used in education. Often it was education that was the driver of the development of electronic technologies. An important stage in the development of e-education was the emergence of the Internet, which has revolutionized and continues to transform and change approaches to education.

The scope of application of new electronic technologies in teaching Russian is unusually wide. All these tools allow you to organize the teaching of Russian at a completely different level.

Electronic technologies have a number of advantages: interactivity, multimedia, communication opportunities; they allow you to effectively organize the independent work of students and manage it.

However, given all the advantages of e-learning, it is necessary to take into account its limitations and disadvantages. These technologies should act as an aid, like any other learning tool or textbook. An important aspect for organizing effective work using electronic technologies is both the readiness of teaching staff and the readiness of the electronic educational environment of an educational institution in general. Based on the above conditions, it is necessary to competently build your work using these technologies.

Currently, many types of electronic technologies are used in education: computers, interactive whiteboards, webcams, electronic resources, projectors, etc. Combinations of these technologies make it possible to create complex educational systems, such as a virtual classroom.

This section reviews existing technologies and attempts to categorize them.

E-learning can be divided into two categories based on the possibilities of simultaneous user participation: synchronous and asynchronous.

Synchronous training programs involve the simultaneous participation of all students in them, as in a classroom when a teacher gives a lecture. Synchronous e-learning includes educational web conferencing, topical chats, instant messaging, and virtual classrooms.

Asynchronous training programs allow students to participate in them at different times, when it is convenient and as needed. Asynchronous e-learning includes open-ended courses, historically the most common form of e-learning, as well as message boards, discussion forums, and e-mail mentoring. [8]

It is worth noting that most technologies can act as both synchronous and asynchronous. It depends on their use.

In addition, technologies are divided into general and specialized.

General purpose technologies, such as office applications, webcams, smartphones, are the most accessible tools for use in education. These technologies are widespread and are used not only in education, but also in work, leisure, scientific purposes, etc. The most common technologies used in schools include text editors, audio files, projectors, presentation programs, editors web pages, Internet resources, social networks, e-mail, chats, etc.

Specialized tools, in turn, can be divided into universal (for teaching any academic discipline) and highly specialized (for teaching a specific discipline).

Universal educational electronic resources include:

- creation of educational materials;
- ensuring communication;
- management of the learning process.

The above technologies can be used both for distance learning and for traditional full-time and combined (full-time distance) training courses.

In the process of teaching Russian, all three types can be used.

Let's consider in more detail the technologies for organizing e-learning. In general, modern technologies can be divided into two groups: hardware and software. Often, they are used in combination.

Electronic education hardware is a set of technical means (electronic and mechanical devices) that both ensure the normal functioning of any electronic systems: computers, data transmission networks, and expand their basic functions. [4]

Computers, tablets and mobile devices

Collaborative learning is a group-based approach to learning in which students interact in a coordinated manner to achieve a learning goal. Recent developments in mobile technology enable the creation of highly efficient and productive learning applications. Many app developers and educators are looking to smartphones and tablets as a collaborative learning environment. Computers and tablets allow students and teachers to access websites and various types of files.

Many mobile devices support mobile learning. Mobile learning is closely related to e-learning and distance learning, the difference is the use of mobile devices. Learning takes place regardless of location and takes place using portable technology. In other words, mobile learning reduces the restrictions on receiving education at the location using portable devices. [5]

Mobile devices such as clickers and smartphones can be used for instant audience feedback. [4] Mobile learning can provide productivity support for checking time, setting reminders, getting work materials, and instructions. [3]

Audio technologies

Radio offers a synchronous learning tool, while Internet audio streaming with webcasts and podcasts can be asynchronous. Microphones help students and teachers communicate more clearly with each other. [eighteen]

Video technologies

An example of asynchronous interaction is DVDs with video lectures, but synchronous methods with digital video via a server or web resources are also possible: video streaming via YouTube, Teacher Tube, Skype, Adobe Connect and webcams. Video communications help speakers connect with other experts as well. [1] Interactive digital video games can also be used for learning.

Webcams allow you to create virtual classrooms and a virtual learning environment. Webcams are also being used to combat cheating and other forms of academic dishonesty that can occur in an e-learning environment. [2]

A projector is a device that projects an image onto a screen. It has a number of advantages over traditional visual aids. Image dimensions can be changed. The image is highlighted and better perceived. The teacher himself determines the time and duration of the display of the image or video. It can easily control the sequence and speed of changing images. Images are stored electronically and do not take up physical space in the classroom.

Interactive whiteboard, also known as Whiteboard, is used figuratively to refer to virtual interactive whiteboards, in which a computer and software applications mimic whiteboards, allowing you to write or draw. This type is useful for virtual meetings, collaboration, and instant messaging. Interactive whiteboards allow students and teachers to write on a touch screen. Depending on the settings, this tutorial can be interactive for writing and working with images. [5]

A virtual learning environment (VLE), also known as a learning platform, simulates a virtual classroom or class by mixing multiple communication technologies at the same time. For example, web conferencing software such as GoToTraining, WebEx Training, or Adobe Connect allows students and teachers to communicate with each other through a webcam, microphone, and provide real-time group conversation. Participants can raise their hands, answer questions, or take tests. Students can use the interactive whiteboard (WhiteBoard) and Screencasting if teachers have given access rights for text notes, microphone, mouse control.

A virtual classroom provides an opportunity for students to receive direct instruction from a teacher in an interactive environment. Learners have direct and immediate access to their teacher for instant feedback and corrections. The virtual classroom provides a structured class schedule that can be helpful for students who want the freedom of asynchronous learning. In addition, the virtual classroom provides a social learning environment that replicates traditional "off-line" classrooms. Most virtual classroom applications provide a recording feature. Each class session is recorded and stored on a server for instant access and playback throughout the school year. This can be extremely helpful for students who wish to review material for an upcoming exam. Parents and responsible persons have the opportunity to control any activity. A virtual learning environment (VLE) is especially effective when combined with a management information system (MIS) to create a managed learning environment where all aspects of a course are delivered through a user interface throughout the organization. [10]

Augmented Reality (AR) provides students and educators with the ability to create new layers of digital information that include both the virtual world and real -elements to interact with in real time. There are a number of applications that offer many options and possibilities. e-learning educational lesson.

There are many different types of communication on the Internet. But they can all be divided into synchronous and asynchronous communication. Asynchronous - communication in non-coinciding time periods (for example, a forum or e-mail), synchronous - one-time communication (chat or video chat).

The most common form of communication on the Internet is Telegram. It includes messaging and file transfer over the network. The wide possibilities of this messenger allowed us to open a group named "Rus tilini o'rganamiz" for students and teachers which allows them to communicate online by learning Russian language via online-chatting, films, songs, poems and etc In this Teelegram group, our learners look at practical steps and specific tools for using free publicly available electronic resources and technologies for learning .

Let's consider step by step the application of LT in Russian lesson in our group "Rust tilini o'rganamiz": preparation, conducting a lesson (lesson), control and testing of knowledge.

Information technology allows you to organize effective communication between students and teachers. For collaboration, you can use instant messengers, email, social networks and wiki resources.

Modern messengers allow not only two participants to interact, but also create groups (or channels) where many participants can communicate. An example is Telegram, WhatsApp, Skype, Messenger, etc.

As we have seen, the use of modern electronic technologies in education is an extremely topical issue. Achieving the most important goal of the state, namely, increasing the availability and quality of education, is impossible without the introduction of modern electronic technologies in the field of education. This is reflected in the State Educational Standard of Secondary Education, in which an important place is given to the use of information technology, including in terms of teaching Russian.

And although electronic means in education have existed for a long time, at present, modern computers and the Internet have become widespread and widely available, and the emerging technologies allow organizing education at a completely different quality level. The use of modern technologies not only does not contradict didactic principles when learning a language, but, on the contrary, helps to implement them more efficiently thanks to new opportunities that have appeared. Modern technologies are suitable for the development of students' communication skills and stimulate interest in cognitive activity, meeting the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard. Moreover, the use of electronic technologies in educational activities has many advantages that allow you to more effectively master the curriculum and achieve educational goals. However, in the process of preparing and conducting a lesson, it is necessary to take into account the shortcomings and limitations in the use of modern technologies, such as the problem of the readiness of teachers and the information and educational environment. In the course of the survey, we found that the demand of children for a more active use of information technology in the classroom is extremely high. And although children feel confident with new technologies and actively use them in everyday life, their use is still not enough when learning Russian. To solve this problem, it is necessary to teach students how to effectively use modern opportunities in the process of learning Russian during independent work in the classroom and at home.

As we have seen, there is currently a huge amount of technology, learning tools and a variety of electronic resources that can be used in educational activities.

They allow you to organize learning both in the classroom and in independent work. You can use both universal technologies and very narrow ones for certain specific tasks. The Internet is of increasing importance in education, which provides the widest opportunities for learning foreign languages.

And although some of the considered technologies are still difficult to access and "exotic" for use (complexity, high cost, requirements for the infrastructure of an educational institution), other technologies, on the contrary, are easy to use, widely available and free of charge, which we were convinced during the preparation for the lesson and its implementation.

The use of modern technologies makes the lesson more interesting, students better remember and assimilate information. We are seeing an increase in children's motivation to learn English. Interest in the socio-cultural aspects and culture of the country of the language being studied is stimulated. There is a great demand of students for the use of modern technologies in teaching, which we have seen in practice.

Summarizing above, we can conclude that the current situation provides ample opportunities to improve the efficiency of the educational process. Modern electronic technologies can become an important step in the process of increasing the accessibility of Russian education.

Media resources provide unlimited opportunities for the use of Russian in communication, search, processing, transmission of information and self-development.

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